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Generation of genotype and phenotype data for *Saccharina latissima* strains

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 1.2

CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE, CNRS

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SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 1.2: GENERATION OF GENOTYPE AND PHENOTYPE DATA FOR *SACCHARINA LATISSIMA* STRAINS

OPEN ACCESS *J. Mark Cock¹, Zofia Nehr¹, Philippe Potin¹*

Edited by:

*J. Mark Cock,
Centre National de la Recherche
Scientifique, CNRS,
Paris, France*

Reviewed by:

*Urd Grandorf Bak and
Ólavur Gregersen,
Ocean Rainforest Sp/F
Faroe Islands,*

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Ocean Rainforest

¹ CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE, CNRS, Paris, France

Abstract

This deliverable describes work carried out as part of work package 1 (WP1) of the SeaMark project aimed at generating genotype and phenotype data for *Saccharina latissima* strains that are being employed within the project to breed new cultivars with improved yields and other characteristics. The deliverable describes the extensive sampling that has been carried out to establish pertinent clonal gametophyte strains for the project and the work carried out so far to genotype and phenotype these new strains. The deliverable also describes the genotyping and phenotyping data available for the pre-existing collection of clonal gametophyte strains, which were generated by the EU project GenialG and which constitute part of the strain collection exploited by SeaMark WP1. The conclusion section presents the strategy being implemented to ensure that the work package objectives are attained despite delays incurred as a result of administrative problems with the recruitment of the postdoctoral fellow destined to carry out the breeding work.

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INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to provide information about the work carried on deliverable 1.2 for WP1 of the SeaMark project. The target audience is kelp breeding researchers and aquaculture farmers.

Description of deliverable D1.2:

Report on the genotyping data based on ddRAD-seq and phenotyping data including growth rate, alginate and fucoidan composition will be described based on the screening of more than 300 *Saccharina latissima* strains collected already with the addition of strains from the Faroe Islands, France, and Norway. (Results of T1.2).

SeaMark WP1 aims to implement breeding and selection approaches to generate improved strains of *S. latissima* and *Ulva* spp. Deliverable D1.2 pertains to the *S. latissima* breeding objective of WP1.

The Key Exploitable Results generated so far include the establishment of an extensive collection of clonal *S. latissima* gametophytes that will represent the input material for the genetic crosses planned within the work package in order to identify F1 hybrid progeny with improved production characteristics and other phenotypic characteristics of interest.

METHODOLOGY

Kelp gametophyte sampling protocol

Identification of the samples

Sample names should combine a species code (e.g. "SL" for *Saccharina latissima*), a population code (e.g. "ROS" for Roscoff) and a number (e.g. SL-ROS-7) and be unique relative to the existing Roscoff strain collection.

Metadata:

- Name of the site
- Date and hour
- Tide coefficient
- Corrected depth if subtidal
- GPS coordinates of the site
- Water temperature
- Names of the collector

Material for spore release and gametophyte cultivation

- 50 ml Falcon tubes (1 for each sampled individual) with:
 - 45ml of sterile filtered seawater
 - 2 microscope slides, stacked on each other

- One bottle with freshwater
- Paper towels
- Permanent marker
- Scissors, cutter, or perforating tool

Sampling fertile tissue on the fertile area of the blade (sorus):

1. Note the individual code of the sporophyte on the Falcon tube.
2. Cut four 1x1cm pieces from within the darkest parts of the sorus area.
3. Rinse them with freshwater and clean them with a paper towel.
4. Put the four pieces in a Falcon tube: one at each side of the microscope slides + 45ml of sterile filtered seawater.

Phenotypic determination of gametophyte sex

Saccharina latissima is dioicous. Diploid sporophytes produce spores through meiosis that develop into microscopic male and female haploid gametophytes. When sexually mature, male, and female gametophytes produce either small motile male gametes or larger eggs, respectively. These two types of gametes can be distinguished by microscopic observation allowing phenotypic sexing of the gametophyte individuals. Moreover, even before sexual maturity, male and female gametophyte can be distinguished morphologically (Bi and Zhou, 2014). This allows the gametophytes to be sexed without inducing fertility. Nevertheless, over the course of the EU project GenialG, we noted that this method misassigned a certain proportion of the individuals. Consequently, we decided to determine genetic sex in SeaMark using sex-specific PCR markers. PCR genotyping to determine gametophyte sex.

Sample preparation

Collect a small piece of gametophyte thallus with forceps and transfer to a 20 µL drop of milliQ water. Cut the filament into small pieces with a pipette tip under a binocular microscope. Transfer to a 1.5 mL tube and adjust the volume with to 100µL final with milliQ water. Samples are frozen and defrosted twice before the PCR.

PCR reaction

Table 1: The PCR reaction details.

	Volume (µL)	Final concentration	
Coloured GoTaq (5X) buffer	2.5	1	X
MgCl ₂ (2.5 mM)	1.3	2.6	mM
dNTP (2.5 mM)	0.8	0.16	mM
BSA (1 mg/ml)	0.25	0.02	mg/mL
Sif2057 Forward (10 µM)	0.15	0.12	µM
Sif2057 Reverse (10 µM)	0.15	0.12	µM
Sjm4021 Forward (10 µM)	0.15	0.12	µM
Sjm4021 Reverse (10 µM)	0.15	0.12	µM
Gaz F2 Forward (10 µM)	0.05	0.04	µM
Gaz R2 Reverse (10 µM)	0.05	0.04	µM
GoTaq G2 FlexiPromega (5U/µl)	0.08	0.03	units/µL
H ₂ O	4.87		
Mix	10.5		
Matrix	2.0		
Total	12.5		

Run the PCR at 96°C for 3 min, followed by 10 cycles of 96°C for 40 sec, 65°C (-1°C/cycle) for 40 sec and 72°C for 40 sec, then 25 cycles of 96°C for 40 sec, 55°C for 40 sec and 72°C for 40 sec, and finally 72°C for 10 min (Table 1 and 2).

Analyse a 12.5 µL sample by electrophoresis on a 2.5% agarose gel with appropriate size markers.

Table 2: PCR primers for *Saccharina latissima* sex determination.

Specificity	Primer	Sequence	Tm	PCR product size
Male	Sif2057 Forward	ATGCGACTCCTGTCAATTCC	63°C	186 bp
	Sif2057 Reverse	CTGGGTTGGGTTTTTCATCAC	62°C	
Female	Sjm4021 Forward	GGCTGTTTCAAGCATGGATT	62°C	450 bp
	Sjm4021 Reverse	GCGTCGTCGTTACCTGATTT	62°C	
PCR control*	Gaz F2 Forward	CCAACCAYAAAGATATWGGTAC	57°C	645 bp
	Gaz R2 Reverse	GGATGACCAAARAACCAAAA	57°C	

*These primers amplify the cytochrome c oxidase I (*cox1-5'*) gene which is located in the mitochondrial genome and therefore present in both sexes (Lane et al., 2007).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Sampling and isolation of clonal gametophyte strains

The objective of this part of the deliverable was to isolate clonal gametophyte lines for the regions targeted by the SeaMark project, namely the Faroe Islands, the Brittany region of France and the Reksteren region of Norway. A large collection of clonal gametophyte strains (576 strains) was already available in Roscoff for multiple European sites. This collection was established during the EU project GenialG and the gametophyte strains are maintained in culture. However, additional sampling was required, specifically from the localities of the SeaMark project partners. The pre-existing Roscoff collection had several strains from southern Brittany, suitable for the aquaculture at Algolesco, but no strains specifically from the other two locations (although it does include some Norwegian strains). For the SeaMark project we identified ten strains from southern Brittany (9 from St. Guenolé and one from the Point de Cabellou) and one strain from Norway (from Ny-Ålesund, Kongsfjorden, Svalbard) that were of potential interest for the breeding work being carried out within WP1.

Sampling of new strains from the targeted regions was initiated in Spring 2022, before the official start date of the project to avoid delays with this part of the project. Roscoff exchanged with the following contacts to organise the sampling:

- Elsa Berg and Urd Bak, Ocean Rainforest Sp/F, Mjólkavegur 20, FO-180 Kaldbak, Faroe Islands (www.oceanrainforest.com)
- Mathilde Lemoine, Algolesko (www.algolesko.com)
- Sunniva Tangen Haldorsen, Lerøy Ocean Harvest, Rekstravegen 805, 5683 Reksteren, Norway (leroyseafood.com/oceanharvest)

A standard sampling protocol was used, based on the methodology employed during the GenialG project (see Methodology section).

Table 3: Sampling and sexing of new gametophyte strains.

Country	N° of sites	N° of samples (Sporophyte or mixture of gametophytes)	N° of clonal gametophytes isolated	N° of gametophytes sexed
Faroe Islands*	5	20	480	72
France	4	42	192	105
Norway**	4	9	4	4

*One of the Faroe populations has been lost in culture (summer 2023)

**Gametophyte isolation from these trains is ongoing.

In total, 62 samples were collected, 23 from the Faroe Islands, 32 from Brittany and seven from Norway (Table 3). These samples were treated in parallel with the 11 GenialG samples. The 62 samples were sent to Roscoff either as fertile sporophyte material (49 samples), which was then induced to sporulate, or as pre-isolated bulked gametophytes (13 samples) derived from single or multiple sporophytes. Three of the 62 samples (all gametophyte pools) died and did not give gametophytes.

The gametophyte pools, whether received as pools in Roscoff or derived from sporophyte material, consisted of mixtures of male and female individuals derived from multiple meiosis events (this is the case even if the pool is derived from a single sporophyte because multiple meioses occur in the sorus tissue. To carry out controlled, repeatable genetic crosses, it was therefore necessary to isolate individual gametophyte individuals. A total 181 gametophytes were isolated by microscopic manipulation. These corresponded to 72 Faroe strains, 105 Breton strains and four Norwegian strains.

Genotyping of newly isolated, clonal gametophyte strains

To carry out controlled crosses, it is first necessary to sex the clonal gametophyte strains so that matings are set up between defined male and female strains. A preliminary, phenotype-based analysis (see Methodology section for details) of a subset of 37 clonal gametophyte strains from Brittany (St-Guenolé and Pointe de Cabellou) and Norway classed 18 as females, 18 as males and one as a probable male, indicating that the clonal gametophyte strain collection contains the expected proportions of the two sexes. This phenotypic analysis was based on morphological differences between male and female gametophytes, which allow them to be distinguished under the microscope. However, it can often be quite difficult to assign sex phenotypically. To limit errors, we therefore decided to employ a PCR-based genotyping method (see Methodology section) based on detection of marker genes within the male and female sex-determining

regions (SDRs) of the sex chromosomes (Lipinska et al., 2015) to sex the full set of newly isolated clonal gametophyte strains. Like all kelps, *Saccharina latissima* has a UV-type haploid-phase sex determination system (Lipinska et al., 2017). In organisms with this type of sex determination system, sex is determined by segregation of either the female (U) or the male (V) SDR-containing chromosome to the haploid gametophyte generation (Ahmed et al., 2014; Coelho et al., 2019). Sex can therefore be determined using markers for genes within the SDR regions that are specific for each of the two sexes.

PCR-based genotyping of gametophyte sex was carried out using the method described in the Methodology section. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of the PCR-based sexing of the gametophyte strains.

Origin	Population	Number of females	Number of males	missing data
Faroe	FWT	6	7	11
Faroe	GTA2	4	5	15
Faroe	FUN2	3	3	18
Brittany	LEC	10	13	13
Brittany	PEN	20	13	3
Brittany	STG	16	16	0
Brittany	PDC	1	0	0
Norway	NYA	1	3	0

Figure 1: Example of the results obtained with the PCR-based gametophyte sexing method.

Based on this genotype information, crosses are now being set up to evaluate the growth capacity of F1 sporophyte hybrids generated by mixing fertile, clonal male and female gametophyte strains.

2018 and 2019 at 21 different localities across Europe (Figure 2, Table 5) using the same protocol as that described in the Methodology section above, i.e. the same metadata was collected, and the same strain nomenclature system was used.

Genotyping and phenotyping of the existing clonal gametophyte collection

As mentioned above, a pre-existing collection of 433 clonal *S. latissima* gametophyte strains was established in Roscoff during the EU project GenialG and, along with the newly established strains described in the previous sections, this collection is serving as a genetic resource for SeaMark WP1. The sampling for the GenialG collection was carried out during

Figure 2: *Saccharina latissima* sampling sites for the GenialG collection.

Pools of mixed male and female gametophyte pools derived from multiple independent meiotic events were obtained by sporulation of blade fragments of individual sporophytes. Individual, clonal gametophytes were then isolated from the gametophyte pools by micromanipulation under a binocular microscope. This work was carried out by Marie-Mathilde Perrineau at the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Oban, Scotland) and copies of the strains transferred to Roscoff, where they were sexed using the PCR protocol by Martina Strittmatter in 2022. The collection contains 183 female gametophyte strains, 212 male gametophyte strains and 36 strains of undetermined sex (the latter including eight females and five males based on phenotypic sexing).

The ddRAD-seq method was used to genotype the clonal *S. latissima* gametophyte strains isolated by the Genial project. Briefly, genomic DNA was digested with the restriction enzymes PstI and HhaI and adapters added to include indexes and barcodes before selection of 150 to 600 bp fragments for amplification and sequencing. The ddRAD library was sequenced on an Illumina platform to produce 125 bp paired end reads.

The phenotyping information available for the pre-existing clonal *S. latissima* gametophyte strain collection (GenialG) is indirect data obtained by analysing F1 sporophytes generated by selfing individual sporophytes, i.e. F1 sporophytes were generated by inducing fertility in gametophyte pools derived from individual parental sporophytes and analysing the sporophytes that resulted from male-female crosses within the pool. The data is therefore indirect because the clonal gametophytes isolated from each gametophyte pool are unlikely to have had the same genotypes as the gametophytes

from that pool that were involved in generating the F1 sporophytes (because each pool corresponded to multiple meioses). The phenotyping data generated for the F1 sporophytes does, however, provide some information about the potential or clonal gametophytes derived from the same pool because both were derived from a single parental sporophyte by inbreeding.

Phenotyping data available for the F1 sporophytes includes morphometric measurements of immature (about 10 cm) sporophytes grown under laboratory conditions (10 L carboys with bubbled Provasoli-enriched seawater), metabolite measurements (nitrite, nitrate, ammonium, amino acids, proteins and four different soluble sugars) and barcoding-based microbiome analyses.

CONCLUSION

The sampling and isolation of clonal *S. latissima* gametophytes for SeaMark WP1 has been completed. Together with the previously established (GenialG) collection, Roscoff now holds 614 clonal *S. latissima* gametophyte strains. Both genotype and phenotype data are available for the pre-existing clonal *S. latissima* gametophyte collection and initial genotyping and phenotyping have been carried out for the newly established strains as part of the sexing process. The sampling and isolation of clonal *S. latissima* gametophytes and the genotype and phenotype data collection will be linked to the work task of Triatomic (Carlsberg) in the SeaMark task 1.3: “Development of complete knock-out libraries to study gene function and identify specific genetic variants that have the potential to increase aquaculture productivity” which will start in month 25 of the project.

Unfortunately, genotyping and phenotyping of the newly established strains and the setting up of the planned genetic crosses using clonal male and female lines have been delayed due to administrative problems during the recruitment of postdoctoral fellow (Zofia Nehr) destined to carry out this work. The initiation of the postdoctoral contract was delayed by four months (originally planned for June 2023 but only implemented in October 2023) and this break in the work has necessitated major reorganisation of the planning schedule for the work package. To address this problem, we aim to immediately implement the planned crosses, with the aim of obtaining the first phenotyping data (growth rates) for F1 hybrids in early 2024. In parallel, we have set up optimal, scale-up cultures of all the clonal gametophyte strains selected for the crosses to have sufficient material (0.5 g per strain) available in early 2024 to allow a rapid move to open sea tests of the crosses that performed best under laboratory conditions. Part of this material will also be used for ddRAD-seq genotyping of the newly established gametophyte lines but, given the delays incurred because of the problems with the recruitment of the postdoctoral fellow, the main priority will be to move as rapidly as possible to open sea trials of potentially improved F1 hybrids.

Table 5: Populations sampled for *Saccharina latissima* sporophytes during the Genial project.

Population code	Ocean or sea	Country	Region	Location	Site	Latitude	Longitude	Date of collection	N° indiv. sampled
VEN	Celtic Sea	Ireland	County Kerry	Dingle Peninsula	Ventry bay	52.11575	-10.36756	20/02/2018	30
TRO	Norwegian Sea	Norway	Sør-Trøndelag	Trondheim	Ringvebukta	63.45261	10.46119	04/02/2018	30
KOS	North Sea	Suède	Västra Götaland	Tjärnö*	Kosterhavet national park	58.83552	10.99055	27/01/2018	30
PDC > CON	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Concarneau	Pointe du Cabellou	47.85972	-3.91638	20/12/2017	30
LOC	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Locmariaquer	Pointe de Kerpenhir	47.55705	-2.92567	04/12/2017	30
PER	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Roscoff	Perharidy	48.73087	-4.00453	05/12/2017	30
SMA	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Saint-Malo	Saint-Malo	48.65245	-2.03801	05/12/2017	30
PMI	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Lanildut	Parc Marin d'Iroise	-4.79261	48.47902	22/01/2017	30
ATB	NE Atlantic	Scotland	Argyll and Bute	Oban	Atlantic Bridge	56.31620	-5.58350	15/12/2017	30
AMO	Atlantic Ocean	Portugal	Norte e Porto	Viana do castelo	Amorosa	41.64187	-8.82340	03/02/2018	30
ESP	Atlantic Ocean	Spain	Uia	Ría de Muros y Noya	Punta Polveira	42.78667	-8.96611	20/02/2019	19
TRA	Celtic Sea	Ireland	County Clare	New Quay	Tra Li	53.15625	-9.07312	20/02/2019	21
PIR	NE Atlantic	France	Pays de la Loire	Vendee	Piriac-sur-mer	47.38189	-2.53866	06/12/2018	20
PTW	NE Atlantic	England	Southwest	Cornwall	Porthallow	-50.06919	-5.08119	20/03/2019	10
LOC	NE Atlantic	France	Bretagne	Locmariaquer	Pointe de Kerpenhir	47.55705	-2.92567	21/04/2019	9
POR	North Sea	Scotland	Highlands	Tarbat Peninsula	Portmahomack	57.83290	-3.84350	24/01/2019	25
AUD	NE Atlantic	France	Pas-de-Calais	Cape de Gris Nez	Audreselles	50.83269	1.58602	21/02/2019	22
PER	NE Atlantic	France	Brittany	Roscoff	Perharidy	48.73087	-4.00453	21/02/2019	30
SHI	NE Atlantic	Scotland	Highlands	Shieldaig	Shieldaig	57.52580	-5.65000	06/12/2018	23
EYE	North Sea	Scotland	Berwickshire	Eyemouth	Eyemouth	55.83990	-2.06190	23/01/2019	26
GOT	North Sea	Sweden	Bohuslän	Mollösund	Mollösund	58.06367	11.47574	07/02/2019	25
NOR	NE Atlantic	France	Loire-Atlantique	Noirmoutier	Pointe du Devin	46.99128	-2.30273	22/01/2019	17
HEL	North Sea	Germany	Helgoland	Helgoland	Helgoland Kurpromenade beach	54.18180	7.89155	21/03/2019	32

DATASETS

The clonal *S. latissima* gametophytes have all been assigned unique identifiers and comprehensive information about the strains, including geographical origin, sampling metadata, sex and genotyping and phenotyping information is being recorded as it is generated. For the moment, this information is held in-house in Roscoff, but it will be submitted to public repositories when appropriate.

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